

Importance of Hotel Property Maintenance Management System

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Abstract:- In Sri Lanka, the hotel industry is developing day by day due to local people and tourism. As in the hotel, there are different types of property to manage. Property maintenance management is a very important process when it comes to the hotel industry as it's all about the proper supply of facilities and services. Without maintaining the property the industry cannot achieve its goals effectively and efficiently. By maintaining the properties of the hotel the relevant organization can increase their profit and they can proceed in their business processes smoothly. Moreover, by developing an effective property maintenance management system we can increase customer feedback more efficiently and can make simplify the functions of hotel staff members and the hotel housekeeping team can easily manage the hotel property maintenance management system. So according to the survey results when developing a hotel property maintenance system it should focus on property maintenance of the hotel such as maintaining and cleaning the garden, Kitchen, Rooms, and pool, and Assign staff members for cleaning and maintenance, Sending reminders for cleaning and maintenance, Sending messages to the relevant parties when there is any maintenance or any cleaning process needed to carry on and Creating reports about cleaning and maintain.

Keywords:- Hotel, Property, Maintenance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Sri Lanka, the hotel industry is developing day by day due to local people and tourism. As in the hotel, there are different types of property to manage. Property maintenance management is a very important process when it comes to the hotel industry as it's all about the proper supply of facilities and services. Without maintaining the property the industry cannot achieve its goals effectively and efficiently. By maintaining the properties of the hotel the relevant organization can increase their profit and they can proceed in their business processes smoothly. Moreover, by developing an effective property maintenance management system we can increase customer feedback more efficiently. So this system focuses on property maintenance of the hotel such as maintaining the cleaning, garden, Kitchen, Rooms, pool, and employers creating reports, by understanding the challenges faced when managing and maintaining the hotel property.

There is no proper way to maintain the property of the hotel, the property is the asset of the organization so without managing and maintaining them properly business may lead to losses. Most of the time maintenance of the hotels failed with the ineffective working pattern of the workforce who are entitled to property management. In most cases, the

service crew has not well planned or assisted the real need of the property to maintain due to lack of communication, time-consuming, and lack of knowledge regarding the specific requirements. So As the manager faced a lot of problems like forgetting the maintains the property, difficulty finding the right person for the maintenance, and difficulty of assign staff members for the maintenance and cleaning process.

Objective:

- Finding the problems in hotel property maintenance management
- Finding the features that are needed for the hotel property maintenance management system

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

(Ghazi, 2016) This study shows that the implementation of a maintenance management system will increase customer satisfaction. It has been evaluated that maintenance can be successful not only by maintenance personnel but also with the participation of all plant employees. To see the importance of maintenance in accommodation facilities, it will be appropriate to compare the hotels with the maintenance management system applied and the hotels that are not implemented in terms of customer satisfaction and maintenance expenses.

(Ozturk, 2019) This study was carried out to assess how Taraba Hotel Management perceived the practice of hotel maintenance. Taraba Hotel is classified as a one-star hotel located in Jalingo, the state capital. The hotel was established in 1992. Multi data collection method was used in the study including questionnaire, interview, and observation. The study recommended more proactive maintenance strategies for the hotel, like preventive and routine maintenance and a maintenance overhaul of current facilities in the hotel to prevent further breakdown and also that proper and effective maintenance management practices were lacking in the hotel which could be the reason for low business output from the hotel in recent years as complained by the staff of the hotel during an interview session.

(Kannan, 2013) Maintenance is the key to providing a better-built environment to building customers and users. Maintenance of the hospitality building is significant as its effectiveness will directly affect the quality of services, which have a direct and significant effect on satisfying customers' wants and expectations. The results of this research also indicate that 'Insufficient funds for maintenance jobs' and 'Lack of skilled personnel in maintenance departments' are the major barriers responsible for the poor implementation of maintenance management. This study provides guidance and references for a better building maintenance management system for Egyptian hotels. It would enable the hotel operators to achieve better

maintenance efficiency through various strategies and practices.

(Sahid et al., no date) This research aims to explore the empirical inter-relationships among maintenance costs, maintenance strategy, resources allocation, outsourcing strategy, benchmarks, and maintenance cost index for hotels in Hong Kong. The success of a hotel relies principally on satisfying customers' wants/expectations through the quality of services (hospitality, guestroom, food/beverage, leisure facilities, if any,) and also cost control, which subsequently relies on proper hotel management and maintenance management.

(Chan, 2008) Throughout the years, the importance of the maintenance function and therefore of maintenance management has grown. The widespread mechanization and automation have reduced the number of production personnel and increased the capital employed in the production equipment and civil structures. As a result, the fraction of employees working in the area of maintenance as well as the fraction of maintenance spending on the total operational costs have grown over the years. In refineries, for instance, it is not uncommon that the maintenance and operations departments are the largest, and each comprises 30 percent of the total manpower. The paper finds that important issues in maintenance management range from various optimization models, maintenance techniques, scheduling, information systems, etc. Within each category, gaps have been identified. A new shift in the maintenance paradigm is also highlighted.

(‘Hotel maintenance management’, 2011) This paper introduces a research project aimed at beginning to identify common issues experienced in the field of maintenance management, and how these issues are being addressed by the companies participating in the research project. Maintenance is a huge and fast-changing industry. The main role players in this industry are the companies with the maintenance need and the providers of software, instrumentation, consulting, and training. This research aims to provide a better understanding of the major factors that have influenced the effectiveness of maintenance management efforts – whether the influence has been negative or positive. This will provide a foundation for future research (Batini, 2016) The rapid growth of the hotel industry has increased the usage of data with the help of a property management system (PMS). It deals with sharing information in a systematic procedure within the organization. The major benefit of data management with PMS is the information can be easily stored and shared between staff members; it is useful during recruitment and when an employee goes on vacation, gets sick, or leaves the organization. This article describes how Data Management in hotels works with a property management system (PMS) and the advantages of having PMS in the Hotel Industry. This paper also focuses on the advancement in PMS with cloud technology for future demands. Data Management become a major task in the hotel industry as the data entered on the PMS by the hotel and data entered from guests on the website will be specific, Hotel PMS need to integrate according to the demand and requirement of the guest with

their preferences and also hoteliers must know which PMS is suitable for their property. By having proper PMS hotels can make a good profit and earn guest satisfaction.

(Ranatunga and Dahanayake, 2020) To compete with the international marketplace, the hotel industry must be able to continually improve its tourism services. To construct an electronic marketplace (e-market), it is an inherent requirement to build a correct architecture with a proper approach of an intelligent system embedded in it. This paper introduces a web-based intelligence that helps in maintaining a hotel by reducing the immediate involvement of manpower. The hotel reception policy, room facilities, and intelligent personalization promotion are the main focuses of this paper. This proposed intelligent management system provides high-level of privacy than the existing conventional manual system with greater reliability. To satisfy the customer's needs, this project work provides a seamless and enjoyable experience for customers (Karunarathne and Silva, 2021) The purpose of this paper is to present the maintenance management status, the purpose of this paper is to present the maintenance management status in Moroccan companies. As a limitation of this survey, it has been the fact that the status of management maintenance in Morocco presented in this paper is issued from a survey conducted essentially in big companies and then those conclusions couldn't be available for SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprise). In the future, a survey that concerns one sector or a specific size of companies in Morocco can be affected, giving more accurate results to obtain an optimized model of maintenance management to be implemented in the companies.

(Hsu et al., 2011) Tourism is a sector that has an important position for economic growth in Indonesia. One of the industries that support tourism development is the hotel industry. Not only local tourists, but foreign tourists also use the hotel industry services. Based on data from the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics, Tourism is a sector that has an important position in economic growth in Indonesia. One of the industries that support tourism development is the hotel industry. Not only local tourists, but foreign tourists also use the hotel industry services. Based on data from the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics.

III. METHODOLOGY

The hotel industry is helping the country to increase the economy, so it's very important to develop the hotel industry by identifying the problems. So the researcher surveyed to collect qualitative information about the users. The survey includes seven questions. The questions have been created to gather information about the hotel employees on the hotel property maintenance management process, identify problems faced when doing hotel property maintenance management, and gather hotel employees' suggestions for the problems that occur in doing maintenance functions in hotels. This research aims to get a clear idea of problems in hotel property maintenance management and find solutions to the problems. The sample size of this research is forty and the researcher has sent the survey through WhatsApp.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the survey are below in graphs 40 responses have given their ideas.

A. Responders occupation

Fig. 1: Responders Occupation

Researchers can see that the majority of the responders are Housekeepers. So that shows that most of the answers are to hotel housekeepers' thoughts

B. Areas that Responders are responsible for

Fig. 2: Responders responsibilities

The above figure shows that most of the responders are responsible for maintaining and cleaning the pool, Kitchen and Less number of responders are responsible for the garden.

C. The way how does the maintenance and cleaning details are managed in your hotel

Fig. 3: Method of managing hotel maintenance

Figure 3 shows that the majority of the hotel they using the manual method for managing hotel property maintenance.

D. Record-keeping system for hotel property maintenance

Fig. 4: Record-Keeping system

As mentioned in the figure, it says that majority of employees haven't record-keeping system for maintenance property of the hotel.

E. Problems faced in hotel property maintenance

Fig. 5: Problems with hotel property maintenance

According to the above figure, most of the responders mention that when doing hotel property maintenance they don't have a proper reporting system

F. Features that need to add when automating the hotel property maintenance management

Fig. 6: Features of the hotel maintenance system

The researcher mentioned five features as Assign staff members to clean/maintain, Sending Reminders for cleaning/maintaining, Sending messages to the relevant parties when there is any maintenance or cleaning process,

Sending maintenance/cleaning summary reports to the manager, and Creating reports about cleaning and maintenance. The majority of responders suggest sending reminders for cleaning/maintenance is important when developing an automated hotel property management system

G. Importance of Communication

Fig. 7: Importance of Communication

According to the responders, most of them mention that communication is important for hotel property maintenance management system

H. Satisfaction with manual hotel property maintenance management system

Fig. 8: Satisfaction with manual hotel property maintenance management system

Focusing on the results majority of responders are not satisfied with the manual hotel property maintenance management.

I. Suitable method for managing a hotel property

Fig. 8: Suitable method for hotel property management

Most of the respondents mention that the best way of managing hotel property maintenance management is automation.

J. Importance of hotel Property maintenance Management System

Fig. 10: Importance of the system

Increasing the reputation of the hotel is the main advantage when the hotel gets by having a hotel property maintenance management system

V. CONCLUSION

The research objectives were to Find the problems in hotel property maintenance management, Find the importance of the hotel property maintenance management system, and Find the features that are needed for developing a hotel property maintenance management system.

According to the survey result, most of the responders are housekeepers of a hotel who are responsible for cleaning and maintaining the garden, pool, kitchen, and rooms. Most of the hotels in Sri Lanka use a manual system for managing hotel property maintenance. A majority of Responders have mentioned that there is no proper recording system and also the responders have faced some problems when doing hotel property maintenance managing in manual such as communication problems, no proper reporting system, and no proper reminding process for the hotel employees to do the hotel property maintenance management system.

A majority of responders are not satisfied with the manual hotel property maintenance management. When creating a hotel property maintenance management system it's important to put features such as sending reminders for cleaning and maintenance, Sending messages to the relevant parties when there is any maintenance or cleaning process, and sending maintenance and cleaning report summary to the manager. Apart from that assigning staff members to clean and maintains features is also important.

So by developing a hotel property maintenance management system with includes these features the hotel staff can gain a lot of advantages such increase profit, attracting customers, and increasing the reputation of the hotel. Especially by developing an automated system for hotel property maintenance management system, the housekeeping team can easily manage their work and the hotel manager can overall manageth the housekeeping process with less energy and less time.

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